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Green Synthesis of Copper Oxide Nanoparticles Using *Artemisia dracunculus* Extract and Their Antibacterial Activity

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Abstract— Eco-friendly synthesis of nanomaterials has gained increasing attention due to environmental concerns related to traditional methods. In this study, copper oxide (CuO) nanoparticles were synthesized using *Artemisia dracunculus* extract as a natural reducing and stabilizing agent. The synthesized CuO nanoparticles were characterized using Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), UV–Vis spectroscopy, Scanning Electron Microscopy–Energy-Dispersive Spectroscopy (SEM/EDS) and X-ray diffraction (XRD). FTIR results confirmed the involvement of plant-derived functional groups in the reduction and stabilization processes. UV–Vis spectroscopy revealed the characteristic absorption behavior of CuO, while XRD analysis revealed the crystalline structure and phase purity of CuO. SEM images showed particle morphology and distribution, and EDX analysis confirmed elemental composition. The antibacterial activity of the synthesized nanoparticles was evaluated against Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria. These findings indicate that *Artemisia dracunculus*-mediated CuO nanoparticles offer promising potential for antibacterial applications.

Keywords: Green synthesis, Copper oxide nanoparticles, *Artemisia dracunculus*, Antibacterial activity

1. INTRODUCTION

Nanotechnology has gained significant importance due to its ability to offer innovative solutions in biomedical, environmental, and industrial fields [1–4]. Nanoparticles can be enabled to exhibit completely novel or enhanced properties based on their specific characteristics, such as size, distribution, and morphology [5]. Nanoparticles can be synthesized using various methods. Nanoparticles synthesized using traditional physical and chemical methods have disadvantages, including high cost, the use of toxic chemicals, and environmental damage [6–8].

Obtaining nanoparticles using green synthesis methods is attracting great interest in scientific research due to their advantages, such as being environmentally friendly, requiring low energy, reducing toxicity, and promoting biocompatibility [9–12]. In green synthesis methods, various biological materials, including plants, bacteria, fungi, enzymes, and even viruses, are used to obtain metallic nanoparticles

[13]. Plants are known as nature's chemical factories and are cost-effective and require little maintenance. Furthermore, the use of plant extracts in nanoparticle synthesis offers advantages over biological syntheses with microorganisms, such as avoiding complex processes that require maintaining microbial cultures. Additionally, the rate of metal ion reduction in plants is faster than in fungi and bacteria due to the presence of water-soluble phytochemicals, as fungi and bacteria require longer incubation periods [14]. Various primary and secondary metabolites found in plant extracts, such as terpenoids, alkaloids, flavonoids, polyphenols, monosaccharides, polysaccharides, proteins, and organic acids, are responsible for reducing metal ions to their nanostructure form [15–17]. Secondary metabolites also play a role as coating agents in the green synthesis of nanoparticles [18].

Copper oxide nanoparticles (CuO NPs) have become a focus of interest due to their easy availability, low production costs, high surface area/volume ratio, antibacterial effect, and optical, catalytic, electrical, and thermal conductivity properties [19]. Due to their substantial surface-to-volume ratio, copper oxide nanoparticles are very reactive, leading to a greater antimicrobial effect [20]. CuO NPs exhibit distinctive properties that make them suitable for numerous technological applications, such as sensing platforms and high-strength structural materials [21], along with remarkable bactericidal properties [22]. It has been well established in the literature that copper-based surfaces are capable of eliminating both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacterial strains through direct contact. In this context, CuO nanoparticles have emerged as promising bactericidal agents with broad-spectrum activity, demonstrating effectiveness against various pathogenic microorganisms such as *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Escherichia coli*, *Enterococcus faecalis*, and *Staphylococcus aureus* [23–25]. The antibacterial activity of copper is primarily attributed to the generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and the release of copper ions [26].

In this study, the *Artemisia dracunculus* plant was used for the synthesis of CuO nanoparticles. This plant is rich in bioactive secondary metabolites such as phenols, terpenes, and alkaloids. In this study, we analyzed CuO nanoparticles using different methods, including UV-Vis spectroscopy, FTIR spectroscopy, SEM-EDX, and XRD. We also investigated the antibacterial properties of CuO nanoparticles against Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria. The findings highlight the suitability of green-synthesized CuO nanoparticles from *Artemisia dracunculus* for use in antibacterial technologies.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Materials

Artemisia dracunculus was purchased from the local market in Turkey. Copper (II) Sulfate pentahydrate was purchased from Merck Millipore and was used as a metal precursor. Distilled water was used throughout the experiment. Sodium hydroxide (NaOH, 98% Merck) was used for pH adjustment.

2.2. Green synthesis of copper nanoparticles

For the green synthesis of CuO NPs, 5 mL of *Artemisia dracunculus* extract was added dropwise into 50 mL of 0.1 M copper (II) sulfate pentahydrate solution and the pH of the solution was adjusted to 10 using 1 M NaOH. After the addition of the extract, the solution was heated at 80 °C for 3 h with continuous stirring in a magnetic stirrer. The resulting solution was centrifuged and the precipitate was washed several times with distilled water to remove any remaining biological extract. Finally, the synthesized powder was dried in a vacuum oven at 60 °C.

2.3. Characterization of CuO NPs

The infrared spectra of the CuO NPs were recorded in the range of 4000–400 cm⁻¹ using a Perkin Elmer Spectrum Two FTIR spectrometer equipped with a Universal ATR. XRD data were collected with Cu-

K α radiation using a Rigaku DMAX 2200 diffractometer with CuK α ($\lambda = 0.15405$ nm) radiation. The ultraviolet-visible (UV–Vis) spectral analysis of synthesized CuO NPs was carried out on a Genesys150 UV–Vis spectrophotometer in the range of 200–700 nm to determine the optical properties and surface Plasmon resonance (SPR). SEM analysis was used to examine the surface morphology of NPs by Hitachi-SU 1510, and simultaneously, Energy Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy (EDX) analysis was performed to determine the distribution and quantity of elements in the structure.

2.4. Determination of antibacterial properties of CuO NPs

To evaluate the antibacterial effect of the synthesized CuO NPs, the agar diffusion (Kirby–Bauer) method was used. *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 6538 and *Escherichia coli* ATCC 8739 were used as test microorganisms.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Characterization Studies

FTIR spectra of green synthesized CuO from the extract of *Artemisia dracunculus* is given in Figure 1. The broad absorption band observed around 3370 cm^{-1} is due to O–H stretching vibrations of the biologically active compounds present in the plant extract, and the absorbed water molecules on the surface of nanoparticles. The absorption band at 1576 cm^{-1} corresponds to conjugated C=C and C=O stretching of aromatic components such as flavonoids and phenolic acids, while the band at 1386 cm^{-1} indicates symmetrical stretching of carboxylate groups of plant polyphenols, revealing the interaction of these components with the CuO surface. The band at 1078 cm^{-1} is attributed to C=O stretching vibrations originating from polysaccharides or terpenes in the plant extract, supporting the presence of an organic coating layer. The characteristic absorption bands at 842 cm^{-1} and 596 cm^{-1} correspond to Cu–O stretching vibrations specific to CuO nanoparticles. The FTIR results demonstrate that *Artemisia dracunculus* extract played a significant role as a natural reducing and capping agent in the green synthesis process.

Figure 1. FTIR spectra of synthesized CuO NPs

The XRD diffraction pattern of CuO NPs is presented in Figure 2. The XRD analysis has confirmed the crystalline structure of the nanoparticles and indicate the green synthesized CuO exhibit a monoclinic structure. The XRD peaks show no other phases observed, which suggests the synthesized CuO NPs have high phase purity.

Figure 2. XRD pattern of CuO NPs

Figure 3 illustrates the UV absorption spectrum for the CuO-NPs. Two major UV-vis absorbance bands were observed, one of which occurs at about 230 nm, while the other appears at about 260 nm. The absorption band occurring at 230 nm is due to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition in aromatic rings obtained from the *Artemisia drancunculus* extract. The band that occurs at 260 nm is caused by $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions as well as ligand-to-metal charge transfers involving Cu-O bond [27–29].

Figure 3. UV-Vis spectra of CuO NPs

SEM image and EDX spectra are shown in Figures 4a and 4b, respectively. The SEM image reveals that the synthesized nanoparticles exhibit a quasi-spherical morphology. The particles appear as

agglomerated clusters, which are composed of smaller primary nanoparticles. This clustered structure indicates a high surface-to-volume ratio, which is beneficial for catalytic and antibacterial applications. The purity was analyzed using EDX spectra showing the highest peak for Cu and O, indicating that the CuO NPs were pure. The weight percentages verify the successful formation of copper oxide.

Figure 4. (a) SEM image and (b) EDX analysis of CuO NPs

Antibacterial tests

The antibacterial activity of the synthesized CuO nanoparticles was evaluated against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacterial strains using the agar well diffusion method. The nanoparticles exhibited effective antibacterial performance against *Staphylococcus aureus* (*S. aureus*) and *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*), as evidenced by the formation of clear inhibition zones around the wells after incubation. Among the tested bacteria, the CuO nanoparticles showed a slightly stronger inhibitory effect against *S. aureus*, with an inhibition zone of 16.2 ± 0.2 mm. In comparison, the inhibition zone measured against *E. coli* was 15.3 ± 0.46 mm. The observed antibacterial activity can be attributed to the interaction of CuO nanoparticles with the bacterial cell membrane, the generation of reactive oxygen species, and the release of copper ions, which may disrupt essential cellular functions and ultimately lead to bacterial cell death.

4. CONCLUSION

In this study, we synthesized CuO Nps using extracts of *Artemisia dracunculus* as a sustainable and eco-friendly reducing and stabilizing agent. Characterization studies successfully verified the formation of CuO Nps via the green synthesis route. The synthesized CuO NPs demonstrated antibacterial activity against both Gram-positive (*S. aureus*) and Gram-negative (*E. coli*) bacteria.

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Author Contributions

All authors contributed to the study and approved the final version of the manuscript. This paper is derived from the first author's master's thesis supervised by the fourth author.

Conflict of Interest (Compulsory)

All the authors declare no conflict of interest.

Ethical Review and Approval (Compulsory)

No ethical approval is required.

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